

Mobile Serious Games in Gamified Nursing Education: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis of Randomized Controlled Trials

Supplementary file

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Table 1 Search strategy

Table S1: Search strategy

Database	Search Strategy
Scopus	"nursing student*" OR "pupil nurse" AND "serious game*" OR "educational game*" OR "game*" AND "mobile*" OR "mobile application*" OR "smartphone*"
Science Direct	("nursing student" OR "pupil nurse")AND("serious game" OR "game-based learning" OR "digital game")AND("mobile" OR "smartphone" OR "app")
IEEE	(Serious Game* OR Digital Game* OR mobile game OR Smartphone* game) AND (nursing student* OR pupil nurse)
SAGE Journal	("nursing student*" OR "pupil nurse*" OR "Student Nurse") AND ("serious game*" OR "smartphone game*" OR "digital game*" OR "gamification")
PubMed	("nursing student*" OR "student nurse*" OR "pupil nurse*") AND ("serious game*" OR gamification OR "digital game" OR "mobile game" OR "smartphone game")
Taylor	("nursing student*" OR "student nurse*" OR "pupil nurse*") AND ("serious game*" OR gamification OR "digital game*" OR "game based learning" OR "gaming" OR "mobile game")
EBSCO	((("nursing student*" OR "student nurse*" OR "pupil nurse*")) AND (("serious game*" OR "game-based learning" OR "digital game*" OR "simulation game*" OR gamification OR "mobile game"))

CINAHL	((("nursing student*" OR "student nurse*" OR "pupil nurse*")) AND (("serious game*" OR "game-based learning" OR "digital game*" OR "simulation game*" OR gamification OR "mobile game")))
CENTRAL	((("nursing student*" OR "student nurse*" OR "pupil nurse*")) AND (("serious game*" OR "digital game*" OR "simulation game*" OR gamification OR "mobile game")))

Figure 1 PRISMA Statement Flow Diagram

Figure 2 Meta-Analysis and Sub-Group

a. Knowledge

Meta Analysis

Model	Effect size and 95% confidence interval					Test of null (2-Tail)		Heterogeneity			Tau-squared					
	Number Studies	Point estimate	Standard error	Variance	Lower limit	Upper limit	Z-value	P-value	Q-value	df (Q)	P-value	I-squared	Tau Squared	Standard Error	Variance	Tau
Fixed	8	0.683	0.094	0.009	0.498	0.868	7.239	0.000	28.234	7	0.000	75.207	0.220	0.161	0.026	0.469
Random	8	0.722	0.193	0.037	0.344	1.100	3.745	0.000								

b. Skills

Meta Analysis

Model	Effect size and 95% confidence interval					Test of null (2-Tail)		Heterogeneity			Tau-squared					
	Number Studies	Point estimate	Standard error	Variance	Lower limit	Upper limit	Z-value	P-value	Q-value	df (Q)	P-value	I-squared	Tau Squared	Standard Error	Variance	Tau
Fixed	8	0.805	0.085	0.007	0.638	0.972	9.434	0.000	47.352	7	0.000	85.217	0.353	0.244	0.059	0.594
Random	8	1.008	0.232	0.054	0.554	1.462	4.390	0.000								

Table 2 Quantitative Data

Knowledge

No	Author, Year	Sub- Variabel	Data								Sample Size	Alpha	SMD/cohen	CI 95%	
			Intervention			Control			MD	F/T				Lower	upper
			Mean	SD	Sample	Mean	SD	Sample							
1	HajiAbad et al (2026)	Learning knowledge outcomes	19.51	3.36	29	13.92	4.15	28				<0.001			
2	Bayram & Caliskan (2019)	Tracheostomy Care Knowledge Test	18.33	2.50	43	16.67	3.75	43				0.568			
3	Farsi et al (2021)	CPR knowledge	7.77	2.46	18	5.44	2.06	18				0.011			
4	Fijačko et al (2024)	Theoretical knowledge of adult BLS			22			21				0.04	SMD (d) ≈ 1.21		
5	Genç et al (2025)	Disaster literacy	46.10	4.93	36	37.82	6.74	38				0.003			
6	Demirel & Kaya (2026)	Post-test IMI Knowledge Total Score	72.00	10.31	30	66.83	13.55	30	5,17	11.275	60	.508		66.16	75.23
7	Kulakaç & Çilingir (2024)	Stoma care knowledge (immediate & retention)	15,4	1,2	45	14,3	2,2	47	1,1	2,688	92	0,009	0.578		
8	Nasirzade et al (2024)	knowledge burn assessment	17.4	2.2	21	14.7	2.6	21				<0.001			

Skills

No	Author, Year	Sub- Variabel	Data								Sample Size	Alpha	SMD/cohen	CI 95%	
			Intervensi			Control			MD	F Hitung/T Hitung				Lower	upper
			Mean	SD	Sample	Mean	SD	Sample							
1	Bayram & Caliskan (2019)	Psychomotor skills	52.67	2.75	43	52.33	2.75	43				0.017			
2	Farsi et al (2021)	CPR skill	25.17	2.81	18	0	0	18				0.001			
3	Fijačko et al (2024)	Practical skills in adult BLS			22			21				0.45	SMD (d) ≈ 0.29		
4	Demirel & Kaya (2026)	IM Injection practice skill	67.10	3.80	30	53.00	5.69	30		11.275	60	.000			
5	Gu et al. (2022)	Skill performance scores	92.00	3.00	77	90.00	3.75	77			154	0.003			
6	Kulakaç & Çilingir (2024)	Stoma Care Skill	57,8	10	45	49,1	7,8	47	8,7	4,517	92	<0.001	0.954		
7	Tang et al. (2023)	skill of venous blood specimen collection	90.10	2.25	52	88.43	3.50	53			105	<0.001			
8	Nasirzade et al (2024)	clinical skills in burn assessment	16.4	2.2	21	11.8	3.8	21				<0.001			

Table 3 Qualitative Data

No	Author (year)	Participant characteristics	Intervention (name of game)	Format games	Kategori game features	Kategori game features 2	Kategori for platform	Duration	Total play time	Final Conclusion
1	Bayram & Caliskan (2019)	1-2 year students	Game-based virtual reality phone application	Simulation+scenario	Simulation	Scenario-based	Mobile phone	Limited duration	1 week	- Knowledge meningkat tetapi tidak signifikan - Game meningkatkan performa psychomotor skill
2	Demirel & Kaya (2026)	1-2 year students	Interactive Digital Game (IDG)	Scenario	Non-simulation	Scenario-based	Mobile phone + mixed platforms	Unlimited duration	1 week	IDG effectively enhances psychomotor skills, reduces specific anxiety, and improves satisfaction as a complementary tool.
3	Farsi et al (2021)	1-2 year students	Virtual CPR serious game	Scenario	Non-simulation	Scenario-based	Mobile phone	Limited duration	2 week	CPR training using both simulation and smartphone-based serious games improved CPR knowledge and skills.
4	Fijačko et al (2024)	1-2 year students	MOBICPR serious smartphone game	Simulation+scenario	Simulation	Scenario-based	Mobile phone	Unlimited duration	2 week	The serious smartphone game improves theoretical knowledge of BLS but does not significantly improve practical skills.
5	Genç et al (2025)	3-4 year students	Structured Digital-Based Education: 1) Natural Disaster Survival mobile serious game; 2) Stop Disaster (computer simulation serious games)	Simulation+scenario	Simulation	Scenario-based	Mobile phone + mixed platforms	Limited duration	>3 weeks	Structured digital-based education improved disaster literacy and preparedness belief among nursing students
6	Gu et al. (2022)	Student in clinical internship	Game-based Mobile App	Simulation+scenario	Simulation	Scenario-based	Mobile phone	Unlimited	1 week	Mobile apps are effective motivational aids that improve procedural accuracy and clinical safety.
7	HajiAbad et al (2026)	3-4 year students	Co-Surgeon	Scenario	Non-simulation	Scenario-based	Mobile phone	Limited duration	>3 weeks	Digital game-based learning significantly improves the reasoning development of surgical nursing students, demonstrating a strong educational effect

8	Kulakaç & Çilingir (2024)	1-2 year students	Serious Game-based Web Application	No Simulation+scenario	Non-simulation	Non Scenario-based	Mobile phone + mixed platforms	Unlimited duration	2 week	Serious game technology has a positive effect on teaching, skill acquisition, and long-term retention.
9	Nasirzade et al (2024)	3-4 year students	BAM Game (Burn Assessment Mission Game)	Scenario	Non-simulation	Scenario-based	Mobile phone + mixed platforms	Unlimited duration	2 week	The serious game (BAM game) significantly improved nursing students' knowledge and clinical skills in burn assessment
10	Tang et al. (2023)	-	Game-based Mobile App	No simulation+scenario	Simulation	Non Scenario-based	Mobile phone + mixed platforms	Unlimited duration	1 week	Game-based apps accelerate the learning curve and provide a safe virtual environment for practice.

Table 4 PRISMA 2020 checklist

Table S7: PRISMA checklist

Section and Topic	Item #	Checklist item	Location where item is reported
TITLE			
Title	1	Identify the report as a systematic review.	Title page
ABSTRACT			
Abstract	2	See the PRISMA 2020 for Abstracts checklist.	Abstract
INTRODUCTION			
Rationale	3	Describe the rationale for the review in the context of existing knowledge.	Introduction, paragraphs 1–4
Objectives	4	Provide an explicit statement of the objective(s) or question(s) the review addresses.	Introduction, last paragraph
METHODS			
Eligibility criteria	5	Specify the inclusion and exclusion criteria for the review and how studies were grouped for the syntheses.	Methods: Search Strategy and Eligibility Criteria
Information sources	6	Specify all databases, registers, websites, organisations, reference lists and other sources searched or consulted to identify studies. Specify the date when each source was last searched or consulted.	Methods: Search Strategy and Eligibility Criteria, paragraph 2
Search strategy	7	Present the full search strategies for all databases, registers and websites, including any filters and limits used.	Methods: Search Strategy and Eligibility Criteria, paragraph 2
Selection process	8	Specify the methods used to decide whether a study met the inclusion criteria of the review, including how many reviewers screened each record and each report retrieved, whether they worked independently, and if applicable, details of automation tools used in the process.	Methods: Search Strategy and Eligibility Criteria, paragraph 2
Data collection process	9	Specify the methods used to collect data from reports, including how many reviewers collected data from each report, whether they worked independently, any processes for obtaining or confirming data from study investigators, and if applicable, details of automation tools used in the process.	Methods: Data Extraction and Management
Data items	10a	List and define all outcomes for which data were sought. Specify whether all results that were compatible with each outcome domain in each study were sought (e.g., for all measures, time points, analyses), and if not, the methods used to decide which results to collect.	Methods: Eligibility Criteria & Data Extraction
	10b	List and define all other variables for which data were sought (e.g., participant and intervention	Methods: Data

Section and Topic	Item #	Checklist item	Location where item is reported
		characteristics, funding sources). Describe any assumptions made about any missing or unclear information.	Extraction and Management
Study risk of bias assessment	11	Specify the methods used to assess risk of bias in the included studies, including details of the tool(s) used, how many reviewers assessed each study and whether they worked independently, and if applicable, details of automation tools used in the process.	Methods: Study Risk of Bias Assessment
Effect measures	12	Specify for each outcome the effect measure(s) (e.g., risk ratio, mean difference) used in the synthesis or presentation of results.	Methods: Data Synthesis
Synthesis methods	13a	Describe the processes used to decide which studies were eligible for each synthesis (e.g., tabulating the study intervention characteristics and comparing against the planned groups for each synthesis (item #5)).	Methods: Data Synthesis
	13b	Describe any methods required to prepare the data for presentation or synthesis, such as handling of missing summary statistics, or data conversions.	Methods: Data Synthesis
	13c	Describe any methods used to tabulate or visually display results of individual studies and syntheses.	Methods: Data Synthesis
	13d	Describe any methods used to synthesize results and provide a rationale for the choice(s). If meta-analysis was performed, describe the model(s), method(s) to identify the presence and extent of statistical heterogeneity, and software package(s) used.	Methods: Data Synthesis
	13e	Describe any methods used to explore possible causes of heterogeneity among study results (e.g., subgroup analysis, meta-regression).	Methods: Data Synthesis
	13f	Describe any sensitivity analyses conducted to assess robustness of the synthesized results.	Methods: Data Synthesis
Reporting bias assessment	14	Describe any methods used to assess risk of bias due to missing results in a synthesis (arising from reporting biases).	Methods: Data Synthesis
Certainty assessment	15	Describe any methods used to assess certainty (or confidence) in the body of evidence for an outcome.	Not reported
RESULTS			
Study selection	16a	Describe the results of the search and selection process, from the number of records identified in the search to the number of studies included in the review, ideally using a flow diagram.	Results: Selection of Studies & Figure 2
	16b	Cite studies that might appear to meet the inclusion criteria, but which were excluded, and explain why they were excluded.	Results: Selection of Studies
Study characteristic	17	Cite each included study and present its characteristics.	Results: Study Characteristics & Table

Section and Topic	Item #	Checklist item	Location where item is reported
s			2
Risk of bias in studies	18	Present assessments of risk of bias for each included study.	Results: Study Risk of Bias Assessment & Table 1
Results of individual studies	19	For all outcomes, present, for each study: (a) summary statistics for each group (where appropriate) and (b) an effect estimate and its precision (e.g. confidence/credible interval), ideally using structured tables or plots.	Table 2 & Results narrative
Results of syntheses	20a	For each synthesis, briefly summarise the characteristics and risk of bias among contributing studies.	Results: Effects of Mobile Serious Games Intervention
	20b	Present results of all statistical syntheses conducted. If meta-analysis was done, present for each the summary estimate and its precision (e.g., confidence/credible interval) and measures of statistical heterogeneity. If comparing groups, describe the direction of the effect.	Results, Table 3, & Figures 3–4
	20c	Present results of all investigations of possible causes of heterogeneity among study results.	Results: Test of Heterogeneity and Subgroup Analysis
	20d	Present results of all sensitivity analyses conducted to assess the robustness of the synthesized results.	Results: Effects of Mobile Serious Games Intervention
Reporting biases	21	Present assessments of risk of bias due to missing results (arising from reporting biases) for each synthesis assessed.	Results: Publication Bias
Certainty of evidence	22	Present assessments of certainty (or confidence) in the body of evidence for each outcome assessed.	Not reported
DISCUSSION			
Discussion	23a	Provide a general interpretation of the results in the context of other evidence.	Discussion, paragraphs 1–3
	23b	Discuss any limitations of the evidence included in the review.	Discussion, last paragraph
	23c	Discuss any limitations of the review processes used.	Discussion, last paragraph
	23d	Discuss implications of the results for practice, policy, and future research.	Conclusion
OTHER INFORMATION			
Registration	24a	Provide registration information for the review, including register name and registration number, or state	Abstract & Methods,

Section and Topic	Item #	Checklist item	Location where item is reported
and protocol		that the review was not registered.	paragraph 1
	24b	Indicate where the review protocol can be accessed, or state that a protocol was not prepared.	Methods, paragraph 1
	24c	Describe and explain any amendments to information provided at registration or in the protocol.	Not reported
Support	25	Describe sources of financial or non-financial support for the review, and the role of the funders or sponsors in the review.	Acknowledgments
Competing interests	26	Declare any competing interests of review authors.	Declaration of Competing Interest
Availability of data, code and other materials	27	Report which of the following are publicly available and where they can be found: template data collection forms; data extracted from included studies; data used for all analyses; analytic code; any other materials used in the review.	Methods (implicitly through tables/figures)

Table 5 PRISMA 2020 FOR ABSTRACTS checklist

Section and Topic	Item #	Checklist item	Reported (Yes/No)
TITLE			
Title	1	Identify the report as a systematic review.	Yes
BACKGROUND			
Objectives	2	Provide an explicit statement of the main objective(s) or question(s) the review addresses.	Yes
METHODS			
Eligibility criteria	3	Specify the inclusion and exclusion criteria for the review.	Yes
Information sources	4	Specify the information sources (e.g. databases, registers) used to identify studies and the date when each was last searched.	Yes
Risk of bias	5	Specify the methods used to assess risk of bias in the included studies.	Yes
Synthesis of results	6	Specify the methods used to present and synthesise results.	Yes
RESULTS			
Included studies	7	Give the total number of included studies and participants and summarise relevant characteristics of studies.	Yes
Synthesis of results	8	Present results for main outcomes, preferably indicating the number of included studies and participants for each. If meta-analysis was done, report the summary estimate and confidence/credible interval. If comparing groups, indicate the direction of the effect (i.e. which group is favoured).	Yes
DISCUSSION			
Limitations of evidence	9	Provide a brief summary of the limitations of the evidence included in the review (e.g. study risk of bias, inconsistency and imprecision).	Yes
Interpretation	10	Provide a general interpretation of the results and important implications.	Yes
OTHER			
Funding	11	Specify the primary source of funding for the review.	Yes
Registration	12	Provide the register name and registration number.	Yes